

AN EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL STUDY OF THE EFFECT OF SOME MANUFACTURING DEFECTS

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Abstract

During the manufacturing process of composite structural parts, layer of fabrics or unidirectional prepreg may have to be cut in order to fulfil production requirements. From a general mechanical point of view, cutting fibres in a composite part has a large negative impact on the mechanical properties. However, such interventions are necessary in particular cases, for example due to draping of complex geometries.

A rather extensive test program was launched to investigate the effects of defects that typically could arise during manufacturing. The overall purpose of the test program was to determine knock-down factors on strength for typical manufacturing defects that occasionally arise and sometimes are hard to avoid in production: cuts/gaps and fibre angle deviations.

Four types of specimens were tested, reference, intersection of cuts in adjacent layers combined with a bolt hole, cut in a zero degree ply combined with a bolt hole and specimens with misaligned fibres. The specimens with misaligned fibres were tested with three different fibre angles. In addition to the experimental procedure, FE-analyses utilising cohesive elements were conducted, and after mechanical tests, Non Destructive Investigation (NDI) and fractographic investigations were performed. An excellent correlation between analyses and experiments were obtained.

1 Introduction

The issues related to the effect of defects on composite material parts strength has been studied since the broader introduction of composite parts in aircraft application [1].

The challenge today in manufacturing of composite material articles is to develop components that have more complex geometries and are cost-effective to produce and of the desired quality.

In the process of manufacturing composite articles, cuts in the fabric or pre-preg can be necessary and besides fibre angle deviations might occur especially due to draping effects. For a typical fabric the width is limited, and thus a gap is introduced for composite articles of larger size. This is more pronounced for a 45 degree ply but can occur for any ply direction. The effect on strength, i.e. knock-down factors, are therefore of outmost importance.

Bolted joints are very common in aircraft structures for attachment of flight critical components. The strength analysis of bolted joints can, depending on available time, involve analytical methods, semi-analytical approaches [2] or the use of numerical approaches utilising e.g. FE-methods. The failure of the joint is usually due to a combination of bearing and by-pass stresses. The determination of failure typically involves the determination of characteristic curves and distances in failure criteria like Yamada-Sun, the point stress criteria or the average stress criteria [3].

In this case, the analysis has been performed using cohesive elements enabling investigation of effects both in the vicinity of the hole and also between cut and un-cut plies.

Parameters that have been studied in this paper are:

- intersection of cuts in adjacent layers combined with a pin loaded bolt hole
- cut in a 0-degree layer combined with a pin loaded bolt hole
- fibre angle deviations, with three different fibre angles combined with a pin loaded bolt hole

In order to study the effect of these deviations on the bearing strength, specimens were tested and compared to reference specimens without defects. The experimental investigation was supported by FE-analysis, NDI and fractographic investigations.

2 Experimental procedure

The material used for all specimens was 6376 HTA prepreg with a nominal ply thickness of 0.13 mm and a volume fraction of 63.5%. The benchmark stacking sequence for all specimens was:

$[(\pm 45/(0/90)_2/\pm 45/(0/90)/\pm 45)]_{s24}$.

Fig. 1. Type of specimens

Four types of specimens were manufactured as schematically shown in Fig. 1. Of a total number of 24 plies 4 plies were affected by the cut and the intersection of cuts. All specimens were manufactured according to standard autoclave manufacturing procedures.

For specimens of type 4 a fibre angle deviation of 5° and 10° in all plies were investigated, the fibres were also oriented perpendicular to the reference and 45° to the reference.

The bearing strength tests were performed according to ASTM D5961/5961M – 10, Standard Test Method for Bearing Response of Polymer Matrix Composite Laminates [4] unless otherwise specified. The bearing strength is extracted from test results in accordance to the test standard equation:

$$\sigma_c = \frac{P}{d \cdot t_n} \quad (1)$$

where

σ_c is the ultimate bearing strength [MPa]

P is the failure load [N]

d is the hole diameter [mm]

t_n is the specimen thickness [mm]

Fig. 2. Testing arrangement for bolt bearing specimen

Some tests were interrupted at failure initiation which was defined as when the first sound of crack propagation could be heard. These specimens were

Fig. 3 Testing arrangement for bolt bearing specimen, dimension

further analysed with non destructive test methods. The test fixture used in this test set-up differs from the standard set-up as no washers were used to support the hole boundaries. A typical standard fixture is shown in Fig. 2. The specimen geometry is shown in Fig. 3.

All tests were conducted at room temperature using an Instron 4505 tensile testing machine with a 100 kN load cell. The displacements and loads were measured by the internal displacement recorder respectively an internal load cell. The load rate was 1 mm/ min.

2.1 Experimental results

The typical failure modes at a macroscopic level for the bolt bearing specimens tested were compressive failure and delamination due to contact stresses at the hole boundary as shown in Fig. 4.

The average bearing strength decreased at the most with 3% in comparison to the reference material, for specimens of type 2 with the most severe type of defect. For specimens with different fibre angle deviations the strength properties on the contrary improved with up to 7 %.

The average test results are presented in Fig. 5 along with the deviations. The positive effect on the bearing strength in specimens with misaligned fibres could possibly be

explained by the fact that the fibres are more favourable oriented in the load direction.

Fig. 5 Normalised bearing strength and failure initiation for the different specimen types. The error bars shows the maximum and minimum deviation.

A possible mechanism could be that when the zero degree fibres are oriented exactly in the load direction the differences in stiffness between each layer will be larger than if all layers are oriented of-axis compared to the load direction. Consequently, the zero-degree fibres will carry higher stresses in the reference specimens, while the 90- and 45-degree layers have to carry less.

Fig. 4. Typical failure modes at a macroscopic level for a bolt bearing specimen are compression and delamination due to contact stresses from the bolt

3 Analysis

The analysis was focused on the specimens which showed the largest reduction in strength, i.e. specimen of Type 2, applying cohesive elements implemented in Abaqus/Explicit [5] which is known to be a powerful tool to model delamination onset and growth in composite materials [6].

3.1 Basic material data

The engineering constants of the material used (6376 HTA) are given in Table 1.

Table 1: 6376 HTA, engineering constants ([GPa], except ν_{ij})

E_{11}	E_{22}	E_{33}	G_{12}	G_{13}	G_{23}	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}
130	10	10	5	5	4	0.3	0.5	0.5

3.2 Element type, mesh

8-nodes solid elements (C3D8R) were used to model the laminate. Each layer is explicitly modeled taking into account the corresponding fibre orientation. One element through the thickness was applied for all layers. To study the influence of the cut made in specimen of type 2, surface based cohesive elements were used to join the elements in the layer along the cut-line and between the first five layers.

The use of Abaqus/Explicit together with the general contact formulation and a cohesive based contact property was easier to implement as compared to methods and elements commercially available in Abaqus/Standard. It allowed a faster FE model development with fewer parts to consider in the assembly.

The remaining part of the specimen was modeled as linear elastic only, i.e. no damage occurs in 20 of

the 24 layers. The damage initiation and growth was restricted to the region with cuts and intersection of cuts.

3.3 Material model for cohesive zone models

The cohesive zone model is described in terms of traction separation laws for deformations in mode I and mode II along the cut. The stiffness of the elastic part of the traction separation curves is set to the standard values for surface based cohesive element suggested in ABAQUS [5]. The benzeggagh-kenane (BK) formulation is chosen for mixe-mode fracture energies determination during analysis [5].

Table 2: Cohesive zone material properties

σ_{33}	τ_{13}	τ_{23}	G_{Ic}	G_{IIc}	G_{IIIc}	BK
(MPa)			(J/mm ²)			
20	30	30	0.3	0.7	0.7	1.5

The cohesive zone properties used in the analyses are shown in table 2. These values are in good agreement with experimental results reported in [7] and [8]. However, the nature of the material in the cut region can be discussed and considered as a resin reach region, which lead to the use of material data for the resin 6376, with $G_{Ic} = 0.432 \text{ J/mm}^2$ [9]. In addition, the values for G_{IIc} given in Table 2 are obtained from ENF tests. It was shown that the nature of these tests may lead to higher critical fracture energy results [8]. Based on different mode II experimental tests performed in [8], a G_{IIc} value closer to 0.5 J/mm^2 was suggested for HTA-6376.

3.3 FE-results

The average experimental failure load for specimens of Type 2 was approximately 97 % of the mean failure load of the reference specimens (mean value for four specimens of Type 1 and in the following denoted as the reference load).

Fig. 8 Interlaminar damage in specimen 2.0, with cohesive interfaces in the cut area - Damage variable CSDMG (1=fully damaged)

In addition, one specimen of type 2 was tested up to the load at which noises indicating damage initiation could be identified, which occurred at 82 % of the reference load. The extent of damage in this specimen was determined using non destructive testing method C-scan (NDT). Therefore, it was of interest, for comparison purposes, to monitor the extent of damage in the numerical model at a similar load level.

The variable representing damage in the cohesive surfaces is plotted in Fig. 8 at a load level of 82 % of the reference load. The figures represent detailed views of the four first interfaces.

From the simulations, we can see that at a load level of 82 % of the reference load, damage due to the local pressure induced by the pin has initiated and propagated at all interfaces between the first five plies. In addition, the damages along the cuts in the 0° and 90° layers were in some extent more pronounced than the ones in the cuts of the ±45° layers. The size of the damage areas observed in the numerical model will be compared to that observed with C-scan in the fractography part further in this paper.

3.3.1 Discussion

In the current investigation the maximum load level is not determined since only 4 out of 24 interlaminar cohesive regions were considered. Therefore, no damage initiation and growth is considered in the large part of the specimen. In order to quantify the maximum load level, a study of the growth rate of the damaged region as function of the load level is carried out. The results are given for the four interfaces with cohesive based definition (see Fig. 10). The study is based on digital picture analysis of Abaqus contour plots in the hole region.

Examples of the analysed pictures are shown in Fig. 9. The black colour represent the undamaged region *b* and the white colour the damaged area *a*. The damage ratio used in Fig. 10 is determined as the ratio $a/(a+b)$. The grey region in Fig. 9 represents the laminate hole.

Fig. 9 Damage area evolutions during loading - Ply4-Uncut region interface

Fig. 10 Damage area evolutions during loading – specimen type 2 with cohesive elements in the cut areas.

We can observe that for the interfaces ply3/ply4 and ply4/ uncut region, the slope of the resulting curves increase significantly from approximately 80 % of the experimental failure load of the type 2 specimens. However, this tendency is not visible for the other interfaces.

Another method to determine the failure load would be to study of the strain/stress levels around the hole in the region without cut plies and then use a

strain/stress based failure criteria in order to identify possible failure occurrence.

The contour plots of the stress and strain fields at 98 % of type 2 failure load extracted from the FE-model are shown in Fig. 11-12.

Fig. 11 5th ply (0°) - Strain field at 98 % of specimen type 2 reference load and net section (NS) stress - specimen type 2.

Fig. 12. Homogenized longitudinal (X-direction) stress field for bearing stress in specimen of type 2 estimated at 98 % of the type 2 reference load.

At the laminate hole, the variation of the through thickness strain is due to the bending deformation of the pin under loading.

In the net-section (NS) area, the strain at the hole edge is approximately 1.4%, equivalent to a stress of 700 MPa (calculated with a homogenized E-modulus of 50GPa), see Fig. 11. High stresses (>300 MPa) are still observed far from the hole edge (4 mm), which indicates a possible failure of the laminate (tension mode).

The analysis of the contour plot in the bearing region (Fig. 12) shows the presence of a high bearing stress (>660 MPa) far from the hole edge (>2mm). A bearing failure may also be predicted at 97 % of the reference load since the bearing strength at failure is lower than the value observed. Both the net section stress and the bearing stress observed in the un-cut region are above or close to the theoretical failure stress and strain of the material used in the laminate. Failure could therefore be expected at such load.

4 Fractography

Some of the tests were interrupted at signs of damage initiation; the specimens were subjected to non destructive testing (NDT) with respect to the extent of damage. After NDT, the specimens were subjected to fractographic analysis in order to further identify the site and size for the damage. Five (5) specimens were available for fractographic analyses. In this paper, observations from a specimen of type 2 are presented, as the highest strength reduction was obtained for these specimens and the numerical analysis focused on this type of specimen. The experimental average failure load of specimen of type 2 was 97 % of the reference load. For the specimen used in the present C-scan/fractography study, the loading was stopped at 82 % of the reference load.

The fractographic investigation was performed by sectioning and polishing the specimen. After cutting, the specimens were casted in a transparent epoxy. Polishing was performed by the use of a Streuers LaboPol-5 water-polishing machine with a LaboForce-1 fixture. Polishing was performed with stepwise finer silicon carbide grits from P320 up to a P4000 grid. The polished surfaces were studied by the use of an optical microscope

The C-scan pictures showed an anomaly where the plies had been cut. See Fig. 13 where such an anomaly is very clear in the cut perpendicular to the load direction. As also can be seen in Fig. 13, there is indications of damage close to the tool surface. It should be noted that the cuts were made at the upper surface and consequently there are no indications from C-scan that damage has been initiated due to the cuts.

The free edges of the two specimens of type 2 were polished to study if signs of damage initiation could

be seen in the matrix rich region where the cuts had been made. Also several cuts were made closer to the hole boundary to verify that no damage had initiated in the resin rich regions.

Fig. 13. Anomalies in the area of the cut plies of specimen type 2-5. The arrow indicates the load direction

An example of a photograph of the polished free edges is presented in Fig. 14. As seen in Fig. 14, there are no indications of damage in the resin rich region at the cut, close to the hole boundary. However it is noted that the surrounding/underlying layers are curved due to the cuts which will locally reduce the stiffness.

Fig. 14. Polished surface showing the resin rich region and the curved surrounding plies were the plies had been cut.

The specimen was further sectioned with a cut through the indication of damage and the surface was carefully polished, to facilitate inspection of the hole boundary with respect to damage initiation by the use of an optical microscope.

As seen in Fig. 15, damage is present in the five plies close to the tool surface, which is in agreement with the C-scan registrations.

Fig. 15. Damage in specimen of Type 2.

5 Conclusion and summary

The influences of typical manufacturing defects, such as cuts, gaps and fibre angle deviations, combined with a bolt hole have been investigated. Specimens with a 6 mm hole, and different combinations of manufacturing defects were pin loaded in a special fixture.

The bearing strength was reduced with approximately 3 % for specimens with the most severe manufacturing defect; both cuts and intersection of cuts. Defect such as fibre misalignment had a positive effect on the hole bearing strength.

The experimental study was supported by a numerical study utilizing, Abaqus/Explicit, together with a general contact formulation and with cohesive properties in order to monitor the damage initiation and propagation in the CFRP specimens that were tested.

The simulation results show that at an approximate load of 85% of the reference load, the damage has propagated between all layers and in the cuts significantly. The stresses/strains in the un-cut region are also high, indicating a likely failure even in this area. In addition, the use of Abaqus/Explicit together with the general contact formulation and a cohesive based contact property was very efficient and resulted in a shorter computing time if compared to models with conventional 3-dimensional cohesive elements

Fractographic investigation was performed on a specimen where the plies had been cut. No damage could be observed in the resin rich region where the plies had been cut. Ultrasonic C-scan showed that damage initiation was due to contact between the bolt and hole boundary.

Some of the tests were interrupted at signs of damage initiation and the specimens were carefully examined with NDT, using ultrasonic C-scan.

Ultrasonic C-scan indicated damage initiation close to one of the surfaces of the specimen, but also a unexpected indication of damage on the side of the hole where no contact stresses should be present during the tests.

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